

Restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) and random amplified polymorphic DNA (RAPD) analysis of near-isogenic lines (NILs) with *Pi-b*. The blast resistance gene *Pi-b* was introgressed from two Malaysian and two Indonesian cultivars into a japonica background by repeated backcrosses; several NILs were developed. It was suggested that the gene was on the end of chromosome 2 (Shinoda et al 1971).

We studied patterns of RFLP markers around the region and summarized their results as a graphical genotype map (Fig. 1). To obtain markers closer to *Pi-b*, RAPD markers were sought using 800 polymerase chain reaction primers, and a marker cosegregating with *Pi-b* in all the NILs was found and named b-1 (Fig. 1). Although *Pi-b* was introgressed from four cultivars in Malaysia and Indonesia, the nonjaponica type RFLP patterns were identical among the four lines, suggesting a single origin of the gene in all of the cultivars.

Fine mapping of *Pi-b* by F_2 analysis. Through F_2 analysis of 122 susceptible individuals (recessive homozygous) from the crosses of BL1/Nourin 22 and Aichi Asahi/BL1, the map distances between the *Pi-b* and nearby RFLP/RAPD markers were determined with an accuracy of 0.4 cM (Fig. 2a). RZ123 and b-1 cosegregated with *Pi-b*. The centromeric and telomeric flanking markers G1234 and RZ213 were 0.4 cM and 1.9 cM from the gene, respec-

1. Graphical genotype of the indica region introgressed into NILs with *Pi-b*. b1; RAPD marker, RZ, RG; Cornell University markers. G, cDK; RGP markers.

2. Fine mapping of *Pi-b* with F_2 analyses with 170 susceptible individuals (a), and a contig constructed from the cosmid library (b).

tively. Large-fragment Southern blotting indicated RZ123 and b-1 are on the same fragment of 85 kb.

Cosmid library of rice genome. A genomic cosmid library was constructed with an average insert size of 38 kb, with 5 genome equivalents using pWE 15 as a vector. RZ123 and b-1 were shown to be on the same clone. Four steps of walking were

done by the TAIL method (Liu et al 1994) to amplify the end portions of the inserts, and 100 kb was covered (Fig. 2b).

Cited references

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 Shinoda H et al. 1971. Bull. Chugoku Agric. Exp. Stn. Ser. A20: 1-25 [Jpn/Eng]. ■

Effect of botanicals on managing sheath rot of rice

R. Jagannathan and K. Sivaprakasam, Plant Pathology Department, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India

We evaluated the efficacy of neem derivatives, such as neem oil (3%) and neem seed kernel extract (5%); leaf extracts (10%) from Nochi (*Vitex negundo*), white babul (*Acacia leucocephala*) and polyalthia (*Polyalthia longifolia*); standard fungicide carbendazim (500 g ha⁻¹); and insecticide monocrotopos (500 ml ha⁻¹) to control sheath rot caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (Sawada) W. Gams and D. Hawksw.

Susceptible cultivar ADT36 was planted in the field during 1994-95. Leaf extracts, carbendazim, and monocrotophos were applied as foliar sprays at booting and 2 wk later. Each treatment was replicated three times.

Sheath rot incidence was measured as the percentage of tillers affected in 25 randomly selected hills plot⁻¹ at 20 d after the last spray.

All treatments significantly reduced sheath rot compared with the control (see

Effect of botanicals on sheath rot incidence.

Treatment	Dose (%)	Mean sheath rot incidence (%)	Mean grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)
Neem oil	3	8.18	5.1
Neem seed kernel extract	5	7.79	5.7
Nochi	10	11.25	6.3
White babul	10	8.14	6.1
Polyalthia	10	10.83	6.1
Carbendazim	500 g ha ⁻¹	4.71	6.6
Monocrotophos	500 ml ha ⁻¹	14.54	5.7
Untreated control	-	18.58	5.1
CD (P = 0.05)		2.88	0.9

table). Plants treated with neem seed kernel extract, Nochi, white babul, *polyalthia*, and carbendazim yielded more than the control (see table). ■

Efficacy of *Ipomoea cornea* in controlling rice sheath rot

S. Eswaramurthy, Plant Pathology Department (PPD), Agricultural College and Research Institute (ACRI), Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU), Killikulam, Vallanad 627252, India; V. Mariappan, PPD, ACRI, TNAU, Coimbatore 641003, India; and M. N. Alagianagalingam, K. S. Subramanian, A. Sankaralingam, and E. G. Ebenezer Ponsinghmal Raja, PPD, ACRI, TNAU, Killikulam, Vallanad 627252, India

We studied the efficacy of plant products and chemicals to control rice sheath rot caused by *Sarocladium oryzae*.

Field trials were conducted during 1993 dry (kharif) season. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with 10 treatments (see table) and three replications. The 25-d-old seedlings of cultivar ADT36 were planted at 15- × 10-cm spacing in 5- × 2-m plots. One trial was performed under artificial inoculation conditions and the other under natural infection conditions. The trials were

simultaneously conducted in adjacent fields.

In the artificial inoculation trial, the syringe inoculation method was used because of its greater efficacy when compared with other methods. In each plot, 200 unemerged panicles were syringe-inoculated with 0.2 ml of spore suspension that contained 104 conidia ml⁻¹.

The first spraying was carried out 24 h after inoculation. The second spraying was done 15 d later. The plant products used were *Ipomoea cornea* leaf extract (10%), *Prosopis julifera* leaf extract (10%), neem seed kernel extract (5%), and neem oil (3%).

In the natural infection trial, no inoculation was done.

Fifteen days before harvest, 100 inoculated panicles from the artificial inoculation trial and 100 panicles from the natural infection trial were randomly selected to assess sheath rot incidence. *I. cornea* extract, *P. julifera* extract, and Bavistin were highly effective, recording sheath rot incidence of 11.0, 16.3, and 11.7%, respectively, compared with 72.7% in the control under artificial inoculation conditions (see table). The same trend also occurred under natural infection conditions. ■

Efficacy of plant products and chemicals in controlling rice sheath rot.^a

Treatment	Artificially inoculated plants		Naturally infected plants	
	Sheath rot ^a incidence (%)	Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	Sheath rot incidence (%)	Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)
Neem seed kernel extract, 5%	18.3	733	8.3	1208
Neem oil, 3%	20.0	910	5.7	1158
Bavistin, 0.1% + copper oxychloride, 0.25%	17.3	608	7.3	1225
<i>Prosopis julifera</i> leaf extract, 10%	16.3	892	5.3	1033
<i>Ipomoea cornea</i> leaf extract, 10%	11.0	879	4.3	1067
Bavistin, 0.1%	11.7	642	6.7	1121
Dithane M45, 0.2%	18.3	808	9.3	998
Ziram, 0.3%	15.7	692	7.3	708
Copper oxychloride, 0.25%	22.0	992	8.0	1158
Control	72.7	542	38.7	700
CD (P=0.05)	13.2	ns ^b	6.62	ns

^aMean of 3 replications. ^bns = not significant.

Integrated pest management—insects

Effect of steam distillate extracts of rice cultivars on rice thrips

M. P. Parthiban and R. Veeravel, Entomology Department, Annamalai University, Annamalainagar, Tamil Nadu, India

We tested the reaction of 122 rice accessions against rice thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall) under field and screen-house conditions at the Annamalai University experimental farm during July 1993 and 1994. We used a 0-9 scale (Heinrichs et al 1985) to score the reactions.

Steam distillates of six cultivars—highly resistant Ptb33 and IR62, resistant IET12008, susceptible ADT40, and highly susceptible IR64 and Rasi—showing similar reactions under both field and

screenhouse conditions were prepared (Saxena and Okech, 1985) and bioassayed to assess the nymphal mortality of *S. biformis* and effect on fecundity of adults.

Using a hand atomizer, the extracts (see table) were sprayed on individual 21-d-old TN1 seedlings. One ml of suspension containing 2000 ppm of the active ingredient was delivered. Each treatment was replicated five times. Controls with acetone and water sprays were maintained.

Each potted seedling was put into a mylar film cage (45 cm tall × 10 cm diameter) and infested with a pair of freshly enclosed adult thrips. The eggs laid female⁻¹ were counted 3 d after release.

In another experiment with a similar set of treatments (see table), 21-d-old TN1 seedlings were sprayed with 1 ml of extract

Laboratory evaluation of steam distillate extracts of certain rice accessions against *S. biformis*.^a

Treatment (2000 ppm)	Total eggs laid ^b (no.)	Larval mortality ^c (%)
Ptb33	10.8 d ± 0.4	70.0 a ± 4.7
IR62	13.2 c ± 0.6	60.0 a ± 4.7
IET12008	13.2 c ± 0.6	64.0 a ± 4.7
ADT40	12.8 c ± 0.5	43.3 b ± 2.7
IR64	16.2 b ± 0.6	40.0 b ± 4.7
Rasi	14.2 c ± 0.4	39.6 b ± 2.7
Acetone	20.0 a ± 0.6	6.6 c ± 2.7
Control	20.0 a ± 1.0	3.3 c ± 2.7

^aIn a column, means (± SE) followed by the same letter do not differ significantly by DMRT (p = 0.05). ^bFive replications. ^cThree replications.

of each cultivar at the concentration of 2000 ppm. Plants treated with acetone and water alone served as controls. Each treatment was replicated three times. Treated seedlings were confined individually in test